

CONSUMER AGENDA 2025-2030

CREATe RESPONSE TO
THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
CONSULTATION

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Consumer Agenda 2025-2030: CREATe Response to the European Commission Consultation

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Abstract

This working paper develops from a CREATe response to the European Commission's public consultation on the Consumer Agenda 2025-2030. In line with the submission on 28 August 2025, this paper identifies challenges that jeopardise fairness and consumer welfare within the European Union. It highlights five pressing issues: algorithmic profiling-based unfair designs in online games; interference of technological protection measures (TPMs) with exceptions and limitations to copyright; agentic AI and its implications for digital fairness and consumer protection; affinity-based algorithmic pricing as a regulatory grey zone; and legal uncertainty in applying EU algorithmic transparency to music streaming. To address these challenges, the paper proposes reforms including enhanced transparency and design guidance, updates to EU copyright law, explicit inclusion of agentic AI and affinity-based pricing in the consumer protection agenda, and clarification of the consumer law provisions for hybrid platforms.

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Introduction

In support of the European Commission's objectives to empower consumers, foster a fairer, greener, and more transparent marketplace, and establish a strategic framework for EU consumer policy up to 2030, this paper highlights a set of emerging challenges in the digital environment. These challenges risk undermining the principle of fairness and causing significant harm to consumer welfare. The issues identified are: algorithmic profiling-based unfair designs in online games (Challenge 1); interference of technological protection measures (TPMs) with exceptions and limitations to copyright (Challenge 2); agentic AI and its implications for digital fairness and consumer protection (Challenge 3); affinity-based algorithmic pricing as a regulatory grey zone (Challenge 4); and legal uncertainty in applying EU algorithmic transparency to music streaming (Challenge 5). These five challenges warrant further attention in the Consumer Agenda 2025-2030 and should be prioritised within future policy actions. To this end, the paper offers practical recommendations for addressing and mitigating these challenges.

Identified Emerging Challenges

Challenge 1: Algorithmic Profiling-Based Unfair ('Dark') Design Patterns in Online Games by *Weiwei Yi*

We wish to draw the European Commission's attention to the growing prevalence of unfair design patterns in the online environment, and partially in online games, which have thus far received insufficient regulatory scrutiny. While certain practices may resemble the dark pattern categories typically identified on e-commerce platforms or social media,¹ emerging evidence demonstrates that many such patterns do not fit neatly within existing taxonomies.² This classification gap would likely persist even if the Digital Fairness Act (DFA) and beyond (e.g., Digital Service Act and Data Act) were to adopt current mainstream taxonomies of dark patterns.

The underlying cause of this unfitness lies in the distinctive business models and interaction formats of online games. Unlike mainstream online platforms (such as Amazon or Facebook) that rely primarily on advertising revenue, online games are monetised largely through direct in-game purchases and microtransactions. Their immersive, interactive environments extend far beyond

¹ CM Gray and others, 'Mapping the Landscape of Dark Patterns Scholarship: A Systematic Literature Review' (2023).

² Veronika Krauß and others, 'What Makes XR Dark? Examining Emerging Dark Patterns in Augmented and Virtual Reality through Expert Co-Design' (2024) 31 ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction 1.

standardised user interface (UI) logics (e.g., buttons, layouts, colours) and enable complex gameplay designs that can condition, and in some cases control, players' emotional states.³

The lack of specific regulatory oversight for online games, coupled with insufficient policy reflection on their business models and interactive modalities, has facilitated the emergence of system-level unfair designs. These designs may exploit behavioural vulnerabilities to encourage repeated and higher-value in-game spending.⁴ An empirical work-in-progress indicates that certain game companies which provide service to EU consumers employ algorithmic profiling to dynamically adjust gameplay in ways that influence players' purchasing behaviour. For example, Patent JP2023105107A describes techniques for altering game difficulty in real time to prompt purchases, while another patent US9789406B2 outlines matchmaking methods that heighten competitiveness and drive microtransactions. Purchasable 'Loot Boxes' (a lottery-style mechanic common to many games) appear to act as a 'master key' for multiple unfair design patterns, including manipulation of probabilities and game content.⁵

These practices may be either deceptive (i.e., exploiting players' unawareness) or manipulative (i.e., targeting cognitive and emotional biases irrespective of awareness). Both are inconsistent with the principle of fairness and the due diligence obligations established under the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD).

However, none of these predatory dark design patterns in online games has been well-recognised and discussed by EU and national regulators. Current calls and resolutions in dark designs in games have yet to identify the unique HCI logic of game services for users. The current calls for self-enforced mitigations through limitations to in-game currency design would not be enough to tackle the profiling-based unfair ('dark') design patterns in online games, which are the root of user demand manipulation. The continued prevalence of dark game design patterns also illustrates the limitations of existing self-regulatory measures, highlighting the need for targeted intervention by consumer protection legislation.

³ Weiwei Yi, 'Gaming the Mind: Unmasking "dark Patterns" in Video Games' Internet Policy Review <<https://policyreview.info/articles/news/unmasking-dark-patterns-video-games/1739>> accessed 21 February 2025.

⁴ Elena Petrovskaya and David Zendle, 'Predatory Monetisation? A Categorisation of Unfair, Misleading and Aggressive Monetisation Techniques in Digital Games from the Player Perspective' (2022) 181 Journal of Business Ethics 1065.

⁵ 'How Free Is "Free-to-Play" (Episode 2): Dark Monetisation Design Patterns in Video Games • Submission 94 • BILETA 2025' <<https://virtual.oxfordabstracts.com/event/74165/submission/94>> accessed 26 August 2025.

We recommend that the European Commission consider:

First, the European Commission may explore the opportunity to apply and extend the use of the regulatory tools from existing regulations. This includes considering whether the Digital Services Act (DSA) provisions on algorithmic transparency can be applied to a broader range of online game services, which may be identified as 'online platforms' through appropriate interpretations. If the DSA is not an appropriate tool, then ensure that the upcoming consumer protection law (e.g., the Digital Fairness Act) incorporates comparable mechanisms to secure visibility and transparency of in-game design practices.

Secondly, the European Commission may carry out more behavioural empirical research: Fund and support independent investigations into personalisation-driven unfair designs in high-grossing games, including those that condition, entice, or exploit player vulnerabilities.

Thirdly, it is important to issue design practice guidance: Building on the European Data Protection Board's (EDPB) dark pattern guidelines for social media, develop best practice guidelines for online games. These should specify design features that contravene the fairness principle and set clear expectations for compliance.⁶

Overall, addressing unfair ('dark') design practices in the digital sphere and especially paying attention to the emerging manipulative designs in online games will complement existing consumer protection initiatives (e.g., on restricting virtual currencies and UI level dark patterns in games).⁷ It will also strengthen protections for vulnerable consumers, including children and neurodivergent individuals, who are particularly susceptible to manipulative game design.

Challenge 2: Interference of Technological Protection Measures (TPMs) with Exceptions and Limitations to Copyright by Kristofer Erickson

The promotion of a fair digital economy is hindered by the overprotection of copyright through technological protection measures (TPMs). TPMs are digital locks that can be applied by manufacturers to prevent unauthorised access to copyright materials.⁸ However, because TPMs

⁶ Weiwei Yi and Zihao Li, 'Mapping the Scholarship of Dark Pattern Regulation: A Systematic Review of Concepts, Regulatory Paradigms, and Solutions from an Interdisciplinary Perspective' (arXiv, 14 July 2024) <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2407.10340>> accessed 12 November 2024.

⁷ 'Monetising Play: Regulating in-Game and in-App Premium Currencies' <<https://www.beuc.eu/position-papers/monetising-play-regulating-game-and-app-premium-currencies>> accessed 26 August 2025; 'The European Commission Hosts Stakeholders' Talks on the Application of the CPC Network's Key Principles on In-Game Virtual Currencies - European Commission' <https://commission.europa.eu/news-and-media/news/european-commission-hosts-stakeholders-talks-application-cpc-networks-key-principles-games-virtual-2025-06-03_en> accessed 26 August 2025.

⁸ Article 6(1) of the Information Society Directive (2001/29) required Member States to introduce legal measures protecting TPMs. TPMs are broadly defined under the Directive as, 'any technology, device or

can be applied broadly, they often prevent legitimate uses (such as those covered by copyright exceptions). TPMs can interfere with socially beneficial and economically relevant uses, including research and innovation, because they impact a range of information used by researchers, libraries and archives, such as ebooks and ejournals, audiovisual materials, interactive games, online databases and digital media. Even physical devices such as home appliances, automobiles, farming equipment and mobile devices can be impacted by TPMs that restrict access to embedded firmware needed for interoperability, maintenance, and repair.⁹

Consumers and researchers (including libraries, archives and cultural heritage institutions) widely report that TPMs applied to digital materials inhibit core activities such as research, sharing, learning and teaching, as well as other innovative activities such as text-and-data mining and bibliometric scraping.¹⁰ TPMs are a major source of disutility for users, with 48% of institutions and 80% of individuals reporting they would avoid acquiring TPM-protected materials. 78% of researchers reported limits on downloading and access. Current legal processes to request removal of TPMs are cumbersome, slow and under-utilised. Only 37% of institutions and 29% of individuals had made a formal request to a rightsholder to remove TPMs in order to benefit from an exception, with many reporting slow response times or no response at all.¹¹

Based on these empirical findings and reporting by consumers, researchers and cultural institutions, we have two main recommendations: (1) that measures be taken to offset the economic costs of TPMs in the market by requiring manufacturers to take necessary steps to enable access under exceptions to copyright, reducing negative economic spillovers; and (2) that EU copyright law should be updated to clarify that researchers, libraries and cultural heritage institutions may circumvent TPMs for legitimate purposes without having to navigate the administratively cumbersome processes currently required.¹²

component that, in the normal course of its operation, is designed to prevent or restrict acts, in respect of works or other subject-matter, which are not authorised by the rightholder’.

⁹ AD Rosborough, ‘Unscrewing the Future: The Right to Repair and the Circumvention of Software TPMs in the EU’ (2020) 11 *Journal of Intellectual Property, Information Technology and Electronic Commerce Law* 26.

¹⁰ See K Erickson and V Stobo, *Survey on Technological Protection Measures: Impacts for Researchers, Libraries and Archives* (2024) The Hague: Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) programme of the Stichting IFLA Foundation (funded by Arcadia).

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² See AD Rosborough, *Technological Protection Measures and the Law: Impacts on Research, Education and Preservation* (2024) Table 10, ‘Enforcement of Exceptions and Limitations Permitting Circumvention’. For the specific case of lending of electronic books, see K Barr, M Eben, M Frigeri and M Kretschmer, *E-Books: Evidence and Analysis of E-Lending Markets in Europe – Competition Law and Copyright Law Perspectives* (2025). Both reports published by Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) programme of the Stichting IFLA Foundation.

We recommend that the European Commission consider:

Recommendation 1: The EU policy may account more fully for economic costs imposed by TPMs when assessing their impact. Manufacturers and publishers have failed to provide strong evidence that TPMs are necessary to protect and successfully commercialise their intellectual property. In fact, robust economic research indicates the opposite: there are significant commercial benefits to relaxing or removing TPMs to permit interoperability, adding value for consumers and society.¹³ The negative externalities resulting from TPMs might be compared to those caused by pollution, with policy intervention needed to ensure that producers bear the costs for the long-term effects of TPMs.¹⁴ Regulators should consider setting time limits on TPMs to ensure that works are accessible to all once locks become obsolete. These limits should reflect real-world market exploitation of works and be designed to facilitate research and preservation uses. Manufacturers and publishers could be required to design work-arounds when using TPMs to facilitate enjoyment of exceptions, accessibility and interoperability. Recent empirical research has found that legacy TPMs can still cause significant impediments.¹⁵ When knowledge about the implementation of a specific TPM is lost to the passage of time, current users must invest significant labour to reverse engineer it.

Regulators can exert pressure to ensure that contemporary TPMs applied to new works are removable for purposes of future preservation and research. This is already the case in certain jurisdictions.¹⁶ For example, legal deposit of multimedia works at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France must be accompanied by TPM access codes.¹⁷ The Code of the German National Library requires that legal deposits must not be blocked by TPMs. If the TPM cannot be removed, the access codes should be provided.¹⁸

¹³ See for example market studies by J Dörr, A Benlian, C Grau, T Wilde and T Hess, 'Will Abandoning DRM Have a Boomerang Effect on Apple? An Empirical Analysis of Lock-in and Network Effects' (Proceedings of the 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2009, IEEE) 1. K Erickson, J Rodriguez Perez and S Sinha, 'How Much Do Consumers Value Interoperability? Evidence from the Price of DVD Players' (2017) SSRN <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2998767>>. WM Volckmann II, 'A Model of Digital Rights Management with User Disutility' (2024) 20 *Journal of Industrial and Management Optimization* 59.

¹⁴ JA Rothchild, 'The Social Costs of Technological Protection Measures' (2006) 34 *Florida State University Law Review* 1181.

¹⁵ K Erickson and F Rodriguez Perez, 'Technological Protection Measures and Digital Preservation: Evidence from Video Games' (2024) KR21 Project Report <<https://zenodo.org/records/14524481>> accessed 26 August 2025.

¹⁶ See: J van der Hoeven, S Sepetjan and M Dindorf, 'Legal Aspects of Emulation' (iPRES Conference, 2010) 113.

¹⁷ The Law Library of Congress, 'Digital Legal Deposit in Selected Jurisdictions' (2018) <<https://tile.loc.gov/storage-services/service/ll/llgird/2018299330/2018299330.pdf>> accessed 26 August 2025.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

Recommendation 2: Specific exemptions to anti-circumvention should be crafted to enable European researchers, institutions, libraries and cultural heritage institutions to fully empower their users to the benefit of society and the economy. As shown in a survey of research and preservation activities¹⁹, institutions are highly risk-averse in dealing with TPMs, and may avoid using materials at all, due to concerns about copyright. However, in many cases, circumvention is the only practical method of making available digital materials, even when such use is fully covered by a copyright exception.

Currently, Article 6 Copyright in a Digital Single Market Directive (CDSMD) provides for a mandatory exception:

to permit cultural heritage institutions to reproduce works and other subject matter permanently in their collections for preservation purposes, for example to address technological obsolescence [...] by the appropriate preservation tool, means or technology, in any format or medium, in the required number, at any point in the life of a work or other subject matter and to the extent required for preservation purposes.

The problem for preservation is that the CDSMD is not explicit about whether this exception permits circumvention of TPMs required to accomplish the task of reverse engineering and preservation.

While Article 6(4) InfoSoc Directive instructs Member States to ensure the means are available for prospective beneficiaries to request access to TPM-protected materials from rightsholders, this may be impossible where rightsholders cannot be located, or where third-party manufacturers of TPMs are no longer in business (giving rise to orphan TPMs). In the case of legacy products, many of the manufacturers of TPM-protected products are no longer in business or are no longer interested in exercising their rights. Administrative processes to request the removal of TPMs are cumbersome, and costs are likely to multiply to unacceptable levels for mass digitisation initiatives.²⁰ Unnecessarily hindering users and CHIs should be weighed carefully against consumer benefits and wider benefits to the digital economy.

There have been calls for greater collaboration between digital producers and the research/preservation sector.²¹ Open and fair access benefits consumers as well as society more broadly. Museums, archives and libraries serve as repositories of innovation and

¹⁹ See K Erickson and V Stobo, *Survey on Technological Protection Measures: Impacts for Researchers, Libraries and Archives* (2024) The Hague: Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) programme of the Stichting IFLA Foundation (funded by Arcadia).

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ See A Bachell and M Barr, 'Video game preservation in the UK: A survey of records management practices.' *International Journal of Digital Curation* 9.2 (2014): 139-170; H Stuckey and M Swalwell, 'Retro-Computing Community Sites and the Museum,' *Handbook of digital games* (2014): 523-547.

inspiration for future production, and they enable research and innovation by providing access to knowledge.

Challenge 3: Agentic AI and its Ramifications to Digital Fairness and Consumer Protection by Zihao Li

Agentic AI has become the next generation of artificial intelligence, which has more capability and autonomy to invoke various tools (such as a browser) and perform multi-step tasks on behalf of users. Unlike the traditional foundation models and AI Agents, it normally includes multi-agent interaction where each Agent is coordinated in an orchestrated architecture to fulfil the final tasks. In the context of digital markets, Agentic AI will quietly change who transacts (through autonomous agents acting for consumers), how offers are found (agentic search/recommend), and where decisions occur (machine-to-machine contracting). This technological development coincides with a policy debate about the future of the EU consumer protection action plan. As the Fitness Check already surfaces some of the concrete risks around generative AI, automation, chatbots, personalisation, and dynamic pricing, yet current consumer regulatory mechanisms are still not prepared for such a challenge, especially for agentic AI accessing different applications through Model Context Protocol (MCPs). Considering the rapid developments in the field of agentic AI and its potentially transformative impact on digital markets, it is essential for the EU consumer Agenda 2025-2030 to pay more attention to the ramifications of Agentic AI to consumers. Specifically, these anti-consumer risks include:

Risks arise from the orchestrated, multi-agent autonomy in LLM-as-a-Judge across the lifecycle. Agents plan, delegate, and negotiate with other agents. In orchestration, emergent behaviours arise that no single trader or model explicitly designed. This risks diffuse accountability: a consumer's outcome (e.g., a subscription renewal or price escalation) is the product of policy chains, including planner → tool-caller → retriever → payment micro-service, where each is 'reasonable' in isolation, yet the system nudges beyond the consumer's intent. When evaluation is run in-agent ('LLM-as-a-Judge'), errors get laundered as authority: the same model family plans, executes, and validates. This collapses independence and invites self-justified mis-selling.

Risks emerge at the shifted access points of consumer interaction, such as search and recommendation by agents. As shopping starts inside assistants and agentic browsers, the 'first exposure' to a product is no longer a page with labels but an answer. Sponsorship, affiliate incentives, and self-preferencing can be embedded in the synthesis, not clearly demarcated as ads. Such product recommendations could conceal subtle manipulation through advertising.

Although accuracy is proposed as a mainstream benchmark for evaluation, such manipulation often proceeds through ‘not being inaccurate’ to nudge consumers.²² Apart from this, there is also a risk of opaque gatekeeping by answer-ranking rather than page-ranking; the choice architecture disappears into the single reply.

Another risk lies in the subject shift from consumers to agents. Consumer law presumes people read disclosures, click ‘order with obligation to pay’, and exercise withdrawal. In agentic commerce, the ‘subject who acts’ is the agent. Without new semantics, we face: (i) consent without comprehension (an agent ‘accepts’ terms the human never meaningfully saw); (ii) rights without rails (withdrawal or cancellation is user-interface-bound while transactions are through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and Merchant Control Panels (MCPs)); (iii) blame without bearer (trader blames the agent; the consumer is left to prove a negative).

Risks may also arise from memory, context, and proactive reasoning. Agents remember preferences, infer states (e.g., fatigue, urgency), and proactively propose purchases. Persistence creates path-dependence: early quirks harden into long-run profiles; mis-inferences become self-fulfilling (‘you buy energy drinks at night infers that you must be price-insensitive at 2 am’). This sustains personalised misrepresentation: not factually false, but contextually slanted to a person’s predicted vulnerabilities. The harm is not a single false claim; it is cumulative steering.

Risks may subsist in the continuous learning/adaptation (dynamic systems, static rules). Agents update skills, tools, and prompts continuously and automatically.²³ The harm surface is moving; compliance designed for a specific user experience decays as workflows evolve. Static disclosure rules miss runtime changes: a compliant version at audit time can behave differently a week later. Risk is regulatory lag by design.²⁴

Hallucinations with transactional effects can be a significant source of consumer harm. Hallucinations cease to be ‘just wrong or nonsense text’ once agents act.²⁵ A fabricated voucher code, a non-existent delivery condition, or a misread cancellation window can trigger real

²² Zihao Li and others, ‘Accuracy Paradox in Large Language Models: Regulating Hallucination Risks in Generative AI’ (2025).

²³ Jinyuan Fang and others, ‘A Comprehensive Survey of Self-Evolving AI Agents: A New Paradigm Bridging Foundation Models and Lifelong Agentic Systems’ (arXiv, 10 August 2025) <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2508.07407>> accessed 26 August 2025.

²⁴ *ibid.*

²⁵ Zihao Li, ‘Why the European AI Act Transparency Obligation Is Insufficient’ (2023) 5 *Nature Machine Intelligence* 559.

purchases, fees, or lost rights. The consumer experiences a truthful interaction backed by a card on file.

Privacy and deep data access-related risks also merit attention. To be useful, agents want to access everything: calendars, email, location, purchase history, loyalty profiles. Cross-context aggregation creates inference risks far beyond single-service profiling. The consumer's most protective choice is often unavailable once an agent mediates everything.

We recommend that the European Commission consider:

Recommendation 1: Agentic AI should be included explicitly in the forthcoming Digital Fairness Act. The scope and definitions should cover agent-mediated B2C transactions and 'agent outputs that materially influence consumer decisions', whether via web-browsing agents or A2A MCPs/APIs. There should be a duty to act in the consumer's best interests as a design principle—a technology-neutral obligation that anchors enforcement against steering contrary to declared consumer parameters. Consumers should also have a right to human fallback, namely a horizontal right to reach a human for complaint or redress in flows mediated by bots or agents. Finally, unfair-practice controls should be extended to the agent layer to address agentic dark patterns (structures designed to mislead agents, not just humans.)

Recommendation 2: Existing regulatory frameworks need to be updated in the Agentic economy. Existing EU consumer and data protection law, while robust on paper, is still written for a human-centric model of commerce. Instruments such as the Consumer Rights Directive (CRD), the UCPD, and the GDPR assume that consumers themselves read disclosures, press confirmation buttons, and exercise withdrawal rights. In an agentic economy, these protections risk losing traction: it is often the agent, not the human, that sees the disclosure, clicks the button, or receives the personalised offer. To keep their protective function, these frameworks need to be adapted so that rights and obligations travel through machine-readable channels and remain enforceable when decisions are delegated to agents.

Recommendation 3: Fairness controls by Agentic AI need to be improved. Agentic AI allows for new ways to enforce fairness and consumer protection through technical means. Developers should deploy governance mechanisms at the orchestration level, for instance, a rule that if one agent's decision could negatively impact a protected group, another agent must review it (a form of automated 'fairness double-check'). Multi-agent setups could be used to avoid single-point failures: one agent might be tasked with ensuring an explanation is provided for each decision, another with sanitising personal data before use, etc. There is active research into aligning these systems with ethical policies (such as feeding company ethics guidelines or regulations into the

AI's goals). Such alignment, if successful, means an AI agent could proactively flag an action as potentially unfair or ask for human approval when crossing a certain risk threshold. In new business use cases, from finance to hiring, this could translate to more consistent adherence to laws and ethical standards than a human-driven process that might overlook things. That is, a well-designed agentic AI might reduce human biases and errors by systematically applying fairness rules. While this is an evolving area, it highlights that these technologies need not be solely a threat to fairness; they can also be a tool to enhance fairness if we intentionally build them to do so.

Challenge 4: Affinity-based Algorithmic Pricing: A Grey Zone in Need of Attention by Zihao Li

In the current debate, the Commission rightly focuses on *personalised pricing* (based on identifiable personal data) and dynamic pricing (based on market conditions such as demand, weather, or time of day). Yet there is a growing form of algorithmic pricing that sits uncomfortably between the two and risks slipping through the regulatory cracks: affinity-based algorithmic pricing.²⁶

Affinity-based pricing uses signals that are not strictly personal data and not purely market-level conditions, but instead group-level or status proxies, for example, charging more to customers with low phone battery, iPhone users assumed to have higher disposable income, or subscribers whose prior commitment is interpreted as willingness to pay more. These signals do not uniquely identify an individual, but they cluster consumers into inferred groups and set prices accordingly. The effect is both concealed and discriminatory, while escaping the remit of the GDPR because affinity data often falls outside the legal definition of 'personal data'.

This form of pricing is uniquely concerning because it undermines informational self-determination without the transparency usually required for personalised pricing. Consumers do not know they are being grouped, cannot contest the basis for group inference, and are unlikely to recognise the harm until much later, if ever. Traditional rights of access, rectification, or objection are of limited help because the data used (battery levels, device brand, membership status) is not classified as personal. At the same time, dynamic pricing defences—justified by supply and demand—do not apply either. Affinity-based pricing thus emerges as a 'grey zone' of digital unfairness, neither covered by data protection nor squarely within existing consumer or competition frameworks.

²⁶ Zihao Li, 'Affinity-Based Algorithmic Pricing: A Dilemma for EU Data Protection Law' (2022) 46 Computer Law & Security Review 105705.

The implications for consumer fairness are serious. First, affinity signals can lead to exploitative segmentation that reproduces social inequalities (e.g., device type correlating with socio-economic status). Second, it entrenches opacity: consumers cannot meaningfully exercise autonomy when they cannot even see the group they are placed in. Third, affinity-based pricing can distort competition by silently redistributing surplus from certain inferred groups to platforms, without any efficiency gains or cost-based justification. For these reasons, the next EU Consumer Agenda should explicitly recognise affinity-based algorithmic pricing as a distinct challenge.

We recommend that the European Commission consider:

Recommendation 1: The forthcoming Digital Fairness Act and the updated consumer protection framework should include: require proactive disclosure when affinity signals (such as device type, battery, or membership status) are used to determine prices, and provide consumers with a meaningful non-personalised option; extend transparency and fairness obligations to pricing based on inferred group characteristics, not only identifiable personal data; explore ex-ante safeguards, including design assessments for pricing algorithms before deployment, combined with standardised audit logs that allow authorities to detect exploitative use of affinity proxies; and reinforce consumer law. The UCPD/CRD should prohibit pricing practices that exploit vulnerabilities through concealed affinity signals, recognising these as a form of manipulative design. Disclosures must be not only informational but also actionable: consumers should be able to opt for a non-differentiated price path and contest unfair segmentation.

Recommendation 2: Future consumer protection law should be better supported by other regulations such as the GDPR and AI regulation, and this should include: clarifying the GDPR's scope for pricing and extending protections to group-based inferences that materially affect individuals, not only personal data processing. Article 22 GDPR ("decisions based solely on automated processing") should be interpreted to cover pricing decisions with significant economic impact, whether based on personal or affinity signals; considering group privacy or collective fairness safeguards, so that individuals in algorithmically inferred groups are not deprived of protection merely because they cannot be uniquely identified; and integrating with Agentic AI regulation. As agents increasingly mediate commerce, they will both obscure and amplify affinity-based discrimination. The consumer agenda must ensure that when Agentic AI search or recommend products, they include not only price transparency but also flags indicating when and how group-based differentials are applied, so that agents can shield consumers from hidden exploitative segmentation.

Importantly, the regulation should not aim to ban all algorithmic pricing. As the literature emphasises, some forms of differential pricing may increase efficiency or deliver targeted discounts. However, affinity-based pricing poses unique risks to privacy, equality, and fairness because it bypasses individual rights while still steering outcomes in ways that consumers neither control nor contest. Without intervention, it will quietly undermine the very promise of a fair digital single market.

Challenge 5: Legal Uncertainty in Applying EU Algorithmic Transparency to Music Streaming by Aline Iramina

We would also like to draw the Commission's attention to the legal uncertainty surrounding the application of the EU algorithmic transparency rules, particularly those of the Digital Services Act, to subscription-based music streaming services.²⁷ As the Commission has noted, there are potential legal gaps in the EU's digital regulatory framework, particularly with regard to the practices of online platforms involving non-intermediated content, which could lead to consumer harm. For example, if playlists are influenced by commercial deals (e.g. Spotify's Discovery Mode) without disclosure, this can constitute unfair commercial practice, as consumers are misled into believing that recommendations are neutral and based solely on their preferences when they are not. Therefore, we call for greater legal clarity and better enforcement of the existing consumer protection regime, as this could be more effective than new legislation in the case of music services and other subscription-based services.

Compared to social media platforms, music streaming services have received far less regulatory attention and public scrutiny regarding their lack of transparency. This does not mean that concerns about this issue do not exist, particularly given how the business models of these platforms have expanded to include a wider range of services (e.g., music, podcasts and audiobooks), tools and activities involving intermediated and non-intermediated content. These also include features, such as personalisation, autoplay and social networking functions (e.g., between artists and fans) as well as game-like elements, such as listening statistics (e.g., Spotify Wrapped and Apple Music Replay) and social media sharing features, which can also encourage prolonged user engagement and compulsive behaviour. In recent years, policy reports and

²⁷ ICPEN annual review showed that a large percentage of the 642 websites and mobile apps they examined that offer subscription services use dark patterns. While the report did not specifically mention music services in its public findings, the review included a broad range of subscription-based services, which could encompass music services. It is worth noting that Spotify has previously been under suspicion for using dark patterns. See ICPEN Dark Pattern in Subscription Services Sweep Public Report (2024) <<https://www.icpen.org/sites/default/files/2024-07/Public%20Report%20ICPEN%20Dark%20Patterns%20Sweep.pdf>> accessed 22 August 2025.

initiatives in both the UK and the EU have stressed the need for legal solutions to address the lack of transparency in the use of algorithmic systems by music services to protect consumers, prevent unfair practices and address streaming fraud.²⁸

While most of the concerns relate to creators' low and unfair remuneration, the importance of algorithmic transparency for consumers is also raised. For example, consumers have the right to know how these services collect and use their personal data and have the right to opt out if they do not want their data to be used for profiling. Furthermore, consumers should be able to make informed choices. This means they should understand why certain music tracks or playlists are recommended to them, particularly in relation to any hidden commercial influence, such as paid placements. This is important for both human-curated and algorithmic playlists. Overall, transparency is important to ensure consumers' autonomy and control and to enable them to make informed choices.

As music services increasingly incorporate user-generated content (UGC), such as users' playlists, concerns are also growing about how these services use automated systems to moderate this content. Similar to social media and video-sharing platforms, services like Spotify, Apple Music and Deezer reserve the right to automatically remove songs, podcasts and playlists that violate their terms of use.²⁹ Playlists, for example, can carry emotional, social and even economic value for users. Therefore, when removing users' playlists and other content, platforms should provide sufficient information to enable them to understand and, where appropriate, challenge these moderation decisions.

In this context, there are questions about how the EU's digital regulatory framework applies to music services to safeguard consumers' rights. When it comes to algorithmic transparency, rules already exist within a fragmented and overlapping regulatory landscape where different laws and regulations may apply to these services. Based on the points raised so far, at least three legal instruments can be mentioned: the UCPD (amended by the Omnibus Directive), GDPR and

²⁸ Sven Maltha and others, 'Exploratory study into bottlenecks and possible incentives for Dutch music productions in the online market' (Dialogic, 11 November 2024) <<https://dialogic.nl/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Dialogic-IViR-Eindrapportage-knelpunten-en-maatregelen-online-muziekdiensten.pdf>> accessed 20 August 2025; European Parliament, 'Cultural Diversity and the conditions for authors in the European music streaming market' (17 January 2024) <<https://oeil.secure.europarl.europa.eu/oeil/en/document-summary?id=1772351>> accessed 21 August 2025; CDEI, 'The Impact of Recommendation Algorithms on the UK's Music Industry' (2023) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/research-into-the-impact-of-streaming-services-algorithms-on-music-consumption/the-impact-of-recommendation-algorithms-on-the-uks-music-industry>> accessed 21 August 2025.

²⁹ For example, following a BBC investigation, Spotify, Apple Music, Deezer and YouTube removed racist, anti-Semitic and homophobic content from their services, including songs glorifying 'Aryan nations' with hateful and racist lyrics. <<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/newsbeat-54613907>> accessed 21 August 2025.

the DSA. However, there are challenges when it comes to the application of these rules due to legal uncertainties and enforcement issues.

The GDPR applies to any business or organisation that processes personal data within the EU, including all types of digital services. It provides for both *ex-ante* and *ex-post* transparency rules under Articles 12 to 22. For example, Articles 13(2)(f) and 14(2)(g) require data controllers to inform individuals when they are subject to automated decision-making, including profiling. Article 15 grants individuals the right of access to information, enabling them to submit subject access requests (SARs) to platforms to know whether their personal data is being processed and, if so, to obtain details about its use. While these rules exist, their effectiveness is questionable. The 2024 Global Privacy Enforcement Network (GPEN) Sweep examined 899 websites and 111 apps across multiple industries and found that most of these services employ ‘dark patterns’, with the most common being the use of complex and confusing language in privacy policies and interface interferences (e.g., language and visual tools) that influence consumers to select less privacy-protective options.³⁰ The main challenge, then, does not lie in the absence of rules, but in enforcing them to ensure compliance.³¹

Following the amendments introduced by the Omnibus Directive, the UCPD now requires digital services to disclose information about their algorithmic systems (e.g., Article 7(4a)). It covers platforms ‘that allow consumers to search for products offered by other, third parties, traders or by consumers,’ such as online marketplaces and app stores, but it can also extend to streaming services, when involving commercial practices like advertising, promotions and other paid features that influence consumer decision-making. The UCPD also prohibits hidden advertising, requiring clear disclosure of paid content.³² Under EU consumer protection law, influencers are often seen as traders,³³ which means that they also have the duty to disclose when content is

³⁰Global Privacy Enforcement Network (GPEN) Sweep Report, <https://www.privacyenforcement.net/system/files/2024-07/GPEN%20Sweep%202024%20-%20%27Deceptive%20Design%20Patterns%27_0.pdf> accessed 21 August 2025.

³¹ Spotify, for example, in 2023, was fined by the Swedish Data Protection Authority for failing to properly respond to data access requests, following a complaint by NOYB - European Center for Digital Rights. See noyb, ‘Spotify Fined € 5 Million for GDPR Violation’ (noyb, 13 June 2023) <[https://noyb.eu/en/spotify-fined-eu-5-million-gdpr-violation#:~:text=Streaming%20Service%20did%20not%20properly,€%205%20Million\)%20against%20QSpotify](https://noyb.eu/en/spotify-fined-eu-5-million-gdpr-violation#:~:text=Streaming%20Service%20did%20not%20properly,€%205%20Million)%20against%20QSpotify)> accessed 12 August 2024.

³² Annex 1 of the UCPD sets out the ‘Commercial Practices which are in all circumstances considered unfair’. This list includes ‘Using editorial content in the media to promote a product where a trader has paid for the promotion without making that clear in the content or by images or sounds clearly identifiable by the consumer (advertorial). This is without prejudice to Council Directive 89/552/EEC’.

³³ EU Commission, ‘Legal Brief #1: European Consumer Law and Influencer Marketing’ (Influencer Legal Hub’ <https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e05a5fcb-64e2-494a-8ec4-042c9d1d7aa5_en?filename=Legal%20brief%201.pdf> accessed 11 August 2024.

sponsored or when they receive payment or other benefits for promoting products or services.³⁴ By analogy, human music curators may be subject to similar transparency obligations.

The same could be argued in relation to the commercial practices between streaming services and record labels. For example, Spotify's Discovery Mode allows artists and record labels to either pay Spotify or accept lower royalty rates to promote their tracks through algorithmically generated playlists. In the US, members of Congress have accused Spotify of deceiving consumers about the commercial nature of their algorithmic recommendations,³⁵ comparing the practice to a digital form of payola. They have questioned whether Spotify was complying with the Federal Trade Commission's Guidelines, which require paid content to be clearly disclosed.³⁶ In the EU, similar concerns arise under the UCPD, as this type of feature or programme is comparable to paid search ranking on online marketplaces. According to the UCPD, failure to disclose such commercial arrangements constitutes an unfair practice in all circumstances.³⁷

In *Peek & Cloppenburg* (2021), the CJEU confirmed that the UCPD prohibits hidden advertising, including advertorials, to protect consumer trust in editorial content and ensure a level playing field for businesses.³⁸ The Court reiterated that such practices are deemed unfair in all circumstances, as outlined in Annex I, point 11 of the Directive. It also clarified that any form of payment, monetary or otherwise, triggers the obligation to disclose the promotional nature of content.³⁹ This suggests that practices such as Spotify's Discovery Model could constitute unfair commercial practices, but greater legal clarity or regulatory guidance from competition and consumer protection authorities would help to protect both consumers and music artists.

Finally, one of the main legal uncertainties involves the DSA. The DSA establishes a comprehensive framework to ensure that digital services operate in a safe, transparent and accountable manner. However, it only applies to intermediary services. In the case of hybrid services that offer licensed or editorial content (e.g., music tracks) mixed with UGC (e.g., users' playlists), it is unclear whether they can be categorised as hosting services, under the DSA, and,

³⁴ Under the UCPD, a trader can be either a natural person or a legal entity acting in the course of a professional or business activity. Thus, its rules apply to both products and services in all economic sectors and cover all types of digital services, including subscription streaming services.

³⁵ Jem Asward, 'Members of Congress Slam Daniel Ek and Spotify Over "Troubling" Discovery Mode Policy' Variety (6 April 2022) <<https://variety.com/2022/music/news/congress-spotify-troubling-discovery-mode-policy-1235226722/>> accessed 11 August 2024.

³⁶ Elias Leight, 'Spotify Expands Access to Controversial Discovery Mode Program' billboard (3 August 2023) <<https://www.billboard.com/pro/spotify-discovery-mode-expands-access-stream-on-event/>> accessed 11 August 2024.

³⁷ Point n. 11 of Annex I of Directive 2005/29/EC (UCPD).

³⁸ Case C-371/20 *Peek & Cloppenburg KG, v Peek & Cloppenburg KG* [2021] EU:C:2021:674, para. 29.

³⁹ *ibid* para. 41.

consequently, whether they are obliged to comply with its transparency obligations. Even if they are considered hosting services, there are questions as to whether they could be categorised as online platforms. This is because Article 3(i) of the DSA defines online platforms as:

(...) hosting services that, at the request of the recipient of the service, stores and disseminates information to the public, unless that activity is a minor and purely ancillary feature of another service or a minor functionality of the principal service and, for objective and technical reasons, cannot be used without that other service, and the integration of the feature or functionality into the other service is not a means to circumvent the applicability of this Regulation.

Consequently, if the UGC is considered ancillary, these services could argue that they are exempt from the transparency obligations imposed on online platforms. The UK Online Safety Act 2023 makes it clear that it covers all platforms (user-to-user services) that allow user interaction with and visibility of other users' content. In contrast, the DSA adopts this concept of 'ancillary' and 'minor functionality features', creating legal uncertainty. This provides services with an opportunity to circumvent their obligations or to select which ones they want to comply with.

Even if the UGC in music services is not considered ancillary or a minor functionality, it remains unclear whether the DSA obligations would apply to the music service as a whole or only to the intermediated content.⁴⁰ In 2025, Spotify started publishing the DSA Transparency Report to comply with the new regulation. The report specifies that 'the data relates to content from users of Spotify's services and not to business-to-business licensed content nor Spotify-produced content', which are governed by different legal frameworks.⁴¹ So, it applies to users' podcasts, but not to the music licensed from record companies and other rightsholders. The report also clarifies that 'while Spotify is a service from which content from Spotify for Creators, Spotify for Artists and Findaway Voices is consumed, Spotify users cannot upload audio or audiovisual content to Spotify,'⁴² reinforcing the distinction between the different types of content on the platform, which is important for its categorisation as an intermediary, hosting or very large online platform.⁴³

Notably, other major music platforms, such as Deezer, Amazon Music and Apple Music, have not published DSA transparency reports for their music services, despite also 'hosting' and

⁴⁰ Under the OSA, if UGC is visible to users, the service will be considered an intermediary and fall within its scope.

⁴¹ Spotify, 'DSA Transparency Report (Reporting Period: February 17, 2024 - December 31, 2024)' (Spotify 2025) <https://www.spotify.com/safetyandprivacy/transparency/eu_20250213_dsa_report.pdf> accessed 1 June 2025.

⁴² *ibid.*

⁴³ Spotify has reported fewer than 45 million average monthly active recipients in the EU, despite having over 180 million active users in the region. See Spotify, 'Information on Monthly Active Recipients in the EU under the DSA' (Spotify, 2024) <<https://www.spotify.com/se/legal/digital-services-act/>> accessed 23 August 2025.

‘disseminating’ UGC. Furthermore, none of these services, including Spotify, have submitted their ‘statement of reasons’ to the DSA Transparency Database, as mandated to all online platforms by Article 24.

Different from VLOPs and VLOSEs, which are officially designated by the Commission, there is no official list of all regulated hosting services under the DSA.⁴⁴ Without clear disclosures, users may struggle to determine which platforms are covered or not by the DSA. This highlights the need for greater oversight by the Commission and the Digital Services Coordinators. At some point, the CJEU may also need to clarify the meaning of certain legal terms, such as ‘ancillary’ and ‘minor functionality’, under the DSA. As online platforms have evolved to offer a variety of services, content and commercial practices, it is important to clarify the scope of the DSA. More legal clarity is important not only for music services, but also for other types of hybrid platforms, such as online games, in the evolving digital landscape.

We recommend that the European Commission consider:

First, clarifying the scope of the DSA before introducing new regulations. Particular attention should be given to how the DSA applies to hybrid platforms, such as major music streaming services including Spotify, Apple Music, and Amazon Music.

Secondly, demystifying the application of the UCPD to commercial arrangements between music services, record companies, and artists, especially where these agreements may result in manipulative personalisation or recommendation practices. For example, platforms use data-driven algorithms to nudge users towards paid content or content that maximises engagement or advertising revenue.

Thirdly, as the Consumer Agenda 2025–2030 aims to benefit both consumers and businesses, greater legal clarity from the Commission, as well as from consumer protection and competition authorities, should also contribute to improving the position of music artists and creators within the digital ecosystem.

⁴⁴ Digital Services Coordinators (DSCs) from Member States can provide guidance to help companies comply with the Digital Services Act (DSA). Some DSCs have mapped and contacted these companies themselves, while others have relied on companies identifying themselves as intermediaries and notifying the relevant DSC. *See* Martin Husovec, ‘TOPIC II – FIDE REPORT ON THE DIGITAL SERVICES ACT AND THE DIGITAL MARKETS ACT – EU Digital Economy: General Framework (DSA/DMA) and Specialised Regimes’ (FIDE – International Federation of European Law 2025) XXXI FIDE Congress | Katowice 2025 88 <https://www.fide-europe.org/xms/files/Katowice2025/REPORTS/T2/T2._EU_Digital_Economy._General_Report.pdf> accessed 12 June 2025.

Overall, it is significant to prioritise legal certainty and effective enforcement of existing transparency rules before introducing new layers of regulation. This approach is essential to addressing dark patterns and ensuring greater transparency and fairness for consumers engaging with music and other hybrid digital services.

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